

Colorimetric and fluorescence recognition of zinc acetate for human breast cancer cell (MCF7) imaging : Development of a logic AND GATE[†]

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Abstract : Condensation of hydrazone derivative of 2-hydroxy naphthalene-1-carboxaldehyde with vaniline generates a yellow azine (HL) derivative that selectively recognise Zn(OAc)₂ both by colorimetric and fluorescence method. A binary "AND" molecular logic gate has also been constructed. Binding constant and lowest detection limit for Zn(OAc)₂ are $1.21 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$ and 2.29 nM respectively. Imaging of Zn(OAc)₂ in human breast cancer cell (MCF7) has been achieved.

Keywords : Azine based probe, zinc acetate, AND gate, MCF7 cell imaging.

Introduction

Zn²⁺ is essential in several catalytic centres and structural cofactors of enzymes and DNA-binding proteins¹. It plays a vital role in neurological disorders like Parkinson's disease, Alzheimer's disease, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, and epileptic seizures². It is present in almost all plants and animal tissues³. It is present in almost all classes of enzymes, particularly in carbonic anhydrase and carboxypeptidase, essential for carbon dioxide regulation and proteindigestion⁴⁻⁶. However, excess Zn²⁺ causes severe neurological diseases, developmental defects and malfunctions⁷. The deviation of normal Zn²⁺ level may causes Alzheimer's disease⁸, epilepsy⁹, ischemic stroke¹⁰, and prostate cancer¹¹.

Zn²⁺ is administered as different supplements like zinc gluconate (ZG), zinc gluconate-glycine (ZGG), zinc gluconate citrate (ZG-C) and zinc acetate (ZA) for its deficiency. Medicinal activity of zinc supplement depends on the sum of all positively charged zinc species produced in solution (iZn) at physiologic pH 7.4. Having the highest iZn value (100%), ZA is the most promising¹². ZA is used for treatment of Wilson's disease that blocks intestinal copper absorption from the diet¹³. ZA lozenges are helpful to decrease the average duration and severity of common cold such as cough, nasal discharge, and muscle ache¹⁴. It has mild antibacterial action and spe-

cific inhibitory effect against respiratory syncytial virus (RSV), the major cause of pediatric lower respiratory tract disease^{15,16}. Direct intra-tumoral injection of ZA has positive impact on prostate cancer growth^{17,18}.

Thus, sensitive and selective determination of traces ZA in human tumor and cancer cell lines after its therapeutic treatment is very essential in medicinal chemistry. So far, none of the two available ZA probes^{19,20} are capable for both colorimetric and ratiometric fluorescence recognition.

On the other hand, several logic gates, viz. AND²¹, OR²², XOR²³ etc. are widely used in computers, circuits and communication purposes. Molecular logic gate plays a key role for miniaturization of the information process involving ions²⁴.

All these facts insisted us to develop a naphthalene based probe (HL) for ZA capable functioning in aqueous media both by fluorimetric and colorimetric method. A binary AND type molecular logic gate has been constructed with two inputs viz. Zn²⁺ and ⁻OAc. The probe is used to image ZA in human breast cancer cell (MCF7) using fluorescence microscope.

Experimental

Materials :

High-purity HEPES, 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde, hy-

[†]In honour of Professor Animesh Chakravorty on the occasion of his 80th birth anniversary.

drazine and vaniline are purchased from Sigma Aldrich (India). $\text{Zn}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is purchased from Merck (India). Solvents used are of spectroscopic grade. All other chemicals are of analytical grade and used without further purification. Mili-Q Milipore® 18.2 M Ω cm^{-1} water is used throughout all the experiments. Shimadzu UV-Vis (Model 2450) spectrophotometer is used for recording absorption spectra. FTIR spectra are recorded on a Shimadzu FTIR spectrometer. Mass spectra are collected on a QTOF Micro YA 263 mass spectrometer in ES positive mode. ^1H NMR spectra are recorded using Bruker Avance 500 (500 MHz). pH measurements are performed with Systronics digital pH meter (Model 335). HCl or NaOH (50 mM) is used for pH adjustment. The steady-state fluorescence spectra are recorded with a Hitachi F-4500 spectrofluorimeter. All spectra are recorded at room temperature. The imaging system is composed of an inverted fluorescence microscope (Dewinter, Italy). Images are captured through an attached CCD camera with the help of Bio Wizard 4.2 software. The microscope is equipped with a 50 W mercury arc lamp.

Synthesis of L1 :

Excess amount of hydrazine hydrate is added to the ethanol solution of 2-hydroxy naphthalene-1-carboxaldehyde and the mixture is stirred for 3 h. The yellow precipitate appeared is air dried to proceed for the next step.

Synthesis of HL :

Synthesis of HL is shown in Scheme 1. L1 (250 mg, 1.344 mmol) is added to vaniline (204 mg, 1.344 mmol) in acetonitrile (40 ml). The mixture is refluxed for 3 h.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of HL.

Slow evaporation of the solvent produces yellow crystals of HL in 92.5% yield (420 mg). The structure of HL is

confirmed by single crystal X-ray structure analysis (Fig. 1). ^1H NMR (Fig. 1, 600 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) δ (ppm) : 3.8605 (3H, s), 6.9223 (1H, d, J 7.60 Hz), 7.2562 (1H, d, J 8.95 Hz), 7.4472 (2H, m, J 10.8 Hz), 7.6382 (3H, m, J 7.55 Hz), 8.0464 (1H, m, J 16.45 Hz), 8.5136 (1H, d, J 19.95 Hz), 8.7527 (1H, s), 9.7490 (1H, s), 10.0005 (1H, s), 13.2492 (1H, s); ESI-MS (Fig. 2) : $[\text{HL} + \text{Na}]^+ = 343.21$; FTIR (cm^{-1}) (Fig. 3).

Synthesis of [ZA-L] adduct :

10 mL methanol solution of $\text{Zn}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (87.8 mg, 0.4 mmol) is added slowly to the magnetically stirred solution of HL (120 mg, 0.4 mmol, 10 mL) in dry methanol. The mixture is stirred for 30 min and kept at room temperature for few days to get white crystalline [ZA-L] adduct. Its ESI-MS spectrum shows peak at m/z , 466.23 (Fig. 4) confirming the formation of the adduct.

Cell imaging studies :

Human breast cancer cell line, MCF7 is grown in DMEM (Sigma, St. Louis, USA) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (Sigma, St. Louis, USA), 2 mM glutamine, 100 U mL^{-1} penicillin-streptomycin solution (Gibco, Invitrogen, USA) in presence of 5% CO_2 at 37 °C. For *in vitro* imaging, the cells are seeded in 6 well culture plate with a seeding density of 10^5 cells per well. After reaching 60–70% confluence, the previous complete media is replaced with serum free media, supplemented with ZA and HL separately at a concentration of 50 and 20 μM followed by incubation for 2 h to facilitate their uptake by cells. The cells are then observed under an inverted microscope (Dewinter, Italy) at different magnifications to examine any adverse effect on cellular morphology. HL treated cells are then incubated with ZA for 15–30 min and observed under an inverted fluorescence microscope at different magnifications using appropriate filter.

Images are taken through an attached CCD camera with the help of Bio Wizard 4.2 software. Control experiment is performed using the medium devoid of ZA.

Results and discussion

The probe, HL is synthesized by condensing hydrazone of 2-hydroxy naphthalene-1-carboxaldehyde with vaniline in 1 : 1 mole ratio in acetonitrile following Scheme 1 and structurally characterized by single crystal X ray

Fig. 1. ¹H NMR spectrum of HL in CDCl₃.

Fig. 2. QTOF-MS spectrum of HL.

analysis. The selected crystal parameters and data are tabulated while its molecular structure presented in Fig. 5.

HL exhibits an emission at 500 nm when excited at

440 nm. Gradual addition of ZA enhances the emission intensity (DMSO/water, 1 : 1, v/v, 0.1 M HEPES buffer, pH 7.4). As the probe have pH sensitive donor site, the

Fig. 3. FTIR spectrum of HL.

Fig. 4. QTOF-MS spectrum of [HL-Zn] adduct.

Fig. 5 Single crystal X-ray structure of HL.

fluorescence enhancement varies with the pH of the medium, the maximum being at pH 7–7.5 region. Hence, the entire studies has been performed at pH 7.4, close to the biological pH (Fig. 6).

No significant fluorescence change has been observed upon addition of other common cations like Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Pb^{2+} and Cd^{2+} to HL (Fig. 7).

HL shows fluorescence enhancement only when both Zn^{2+} and AcO^- ions are present together. Presence of

Table 1. Crystal data and parameters for HL

Identification code	HL
Chemical formula	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃
Formula weight	320.34 g/mol
Temperature	296(2) K
Wavelength	0.71073 Å
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	P 1 21/n 1
Unit cell dimensions	$a = 17.9521(5)$ Å $\alpha = 90^\circ$ $b = 8.3536(2)$ Å $\beta = 105.548(2)^\circ$ $c = 22.7949(7)$ Å $\gamma = 90^\circ$
Volume	3293.34(16) Å ³
Z	8
Density (Calcd.)	1.292 g/cm ³
Absorption coefficient	0.089 mm ⁻¹
F(000)	1344

Table 2. Data collection and structure refinement for HL

Theta range for data collection	2.71 to 28.31°
Index ranges	-23 < = h < = 20, -10 < = k < = 11, -25 < = l < = 30
Reflections collected	56175
Independent reflections	8146 [R(int) = 0.0473]
Coverage of independent reflections	99.4%
Absorption correction	Multi-scan
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on F ²
Refinement program	SHELXL-2014/6 (Sheldrick, 2014)
Function minimized	$\Sigma w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2$
Data/restraints/parameters	8146/0/440
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.010
Δ/σ_{\max}	0.001
Final R indices	4758 data; $I > 2\sigma(I)$ all data R1 = 0.0449, wR2 = 0.1052, R1 = 0.0893, wR2 = 0.1294
Weighting scheme	$w = 1/[\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.0507P)^2 + 0.5229P]$ where $P = (F_o^2 + 2F_c^2)/3$
Extinction coefficient	0.0021(4)
Largest diff. peak and hole	0.143 and -0.136 eÅ ⁻³
R.M.S. deviation from mean	0.029 eÅ ⁻³

either Zn²⁺ or AcO⁻ do not show significant fluorescence enhancement of HL (Fig. 8).

The emission intensity of HL ($\lambda_{em} = 500$ nm) gradu-

Fig. 6. Effect of pH on the emission intensities of HL and [HL-ZA] system ($\lambda_{ex} = 440$ nm).

Fig. 7. Effect of common cations viz. Mn²⁺ (1), Cd²⁺ (2), Ni²⁺ (3), Co²⁺ (4), Mg²⁺ (5), Zn²⁺ (6), Hg²⁺ (7), Cu²⁺ (8), Ca²⁺ (9), Pb²⁺ (10), Fe³⁺ (11), Fe²⁺ (12) and Pb²⁺ (13) on the fluorescence spectra of HL. UV light exposed colours of HL in presence of said cations (top).

Fig. 8. Emission intensity of HL (1 μM) in presence of different Zn²⁺ and AcO⁻ salts (150 μM, $\lambda_{ex} = 440$ nm).

ally increases with addition of ZA (Fig. 9) associated with the enhancement of fluorescence quantum yield from 0.0081 to 0.45 (55.55 fold). Job's plot indicates a 1 : 1 (mole ratio) stoichiometry of the [HL-ZA] system (Fig. 10), also corroborated from its mass spectrum (ESI). The selectivity of HL for ZA is attributed to the combined effects of chelation enhanced fluorescence (CHEF) along with the inhibition of CH=N isomerization. The detection limit of the receptor HL for ZA is 2.29 nM (Fig. 11). Upon addition of ZA to HL, the colorless solution instantly changes to yellow, allowing HL as a colorimetric probe for ZA. Upon addition of ZA, the absorbance at 387 nm due to intra-molecular charge transfer (ICT) of HL gradually decreases with the appearance of a new band at 427 nm that increases up to 1 : 1 mole ratio (HL : ZA, Fig. 12). The appearance of an isobestic point at 410 nm indicates the formation of the [HL-ZA] adduct via a common transition state.

Fig. 9. Changes in the fluorescence spectra of HL (20 μM) upon gradual addition of ZA (0.001-500 μM); λ_{ex} = 440 nm, λ_{em} = 500 nm.

Scheme 2. Proposed binding mode of HL with ZA.

Hill equation²⁵ is applied to determine the binding of HL with ZA : $\log [Y/(1 - Y)] = n \log [G] + \log K_{app}$, where Y , n , $[G]$ and K_{app} represent the fraction of ligand binding sites filled, Hill coefficient, concentration of ZA and the apparent association constant, respectively. Y is

Fig. 10. Job's plot for determination of the stoichiometry of the [HL-ZA] system.

Fig. 11. Emission intensities of HL (20 μM) as a function of externally added [ZA] in (DMSO/water = 1 : 1, v/v, pH 7.4), λ_{em} , 500 nm, λ_{ex} , 440 nm.

Fig. 12. Changes of absorbance of HL (20 μM) upon gradual addition of ZA.

determined by the equation, $(I - I_0) / (I_{\max} - I_0)$, where I_0 , I , and I_{\max} are the fluorescence intensity at 500 nm in the absence, presence and in excess of ZA. The association constant for ZA found as $1.2124 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$ (Fig. 13).

Fig. 13. Hill plot for determination of binding constant of HL to ZA in (DMSO/water = 1 : 1, v/v, pH 7.4).

Fe^{3+} and Cu^{2+} interfere to some extent (Fig. 14) and anions (Fig. 15) do not show any significant interference in the detection of ZA.

Plot of the emission intensity vs added ZA generates

Fig. 14. Relative emission intensities of HL + ZA system in presence of different cations (100 equiv.); DMSO- H_2O (1 : 1, v/v, 0.1 M HEPES buffer, pH 7.4); Mn^{2+} (1), Cd^{2+} (2), Ni^{2+} (3), Co^{2+} (4), Mg^{2+} (5), Cu^{2+} (6), Hg^{2+} (7), Ca^{2+} (8), Na^+ (9), Pb^{2+} (10), Fe^{3+} (11), Fe^{2+} (12), K^+ (13) and Ag^+ (14).

Fig. 15. Relative emission intensities of HL + ZA system in presence of different anions (100 equiv.); DMSO- H_2O (1 : 1, v/v, 0.1 M HEPES buffer, pH 7.4); F^- (1), Cl^- (2), Br^- (3), I^- (4), OAc^- (5), NO_3^- (6), NO_2^- (7), ClO_4^- (8), SO_4^{2-} (9), PO_4^{3-} (10), N_3^- (11).

a sigmoidal graph (Fig. 16) which is linear up to $60 \mu\text{M}$ ZA (Fig. 17) and useful for determination of unknown ZA concentration.

The changes of absorbance have been recorded up to $900 \mu\text{M}$ (Fig. 18), the linearity is observed up to $100 \mu\text{M}$ (Fig. 19), useful for the determination of unknown concentration of ZA.

Fig. 16. Emission intensity of HL vs externally added ZA (0.01– $800.0 \mu\text{M}$ in DMSO/water = 1 : 1, v/v, pH 7.4 (λ_{ex} , 440 nm; λ_{em} , 500 nm).

Fig. 17. Linear region of the plot of emission intensities of HL (20 μM, $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 440 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 500 \text{ nm}$) as a function of externally added ZA in (DMSO/water = 1 : 1, v/v, pH 7.4).

Fig. 18. Absorbance of HL vs externally added ZA (0.01–800.0 μM, $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 440 \text{ nm}$; $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 500 \text{ nm}$) in (DMSO/water = 1 : 1, v/v, pH 7.4).

Fig. 19. Linear region of the plot of emission intensities of HL (20 μM, $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 440 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 500 \text{ nm}$) as a function of externally added ZA in (DMSO/water = 1 : 1, v/v, pH 7.4).

Quantum yield measurements :

Fluorescence quantum yields (Φ) are estimated by integrating the area under the fluorescence curves using the equation,

$$\Phi_{\text{sample}} = \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{standard}} \times A_{\text{sample}}}{\text{OD}_{\text{sample}} \times A_{\text{standard}}} \times \Phi_{\text{standard}}$$

where A is the area under the fluorescence spectral curve and OD is optical density of the probe at the excitation wavelength²⁵. Anthracene is used as quantum yield standard (quantum yield 0.27 in ethanol)²⁶ for measuring the quantum yields of the probe and its ZA complex.

Finally, two inputs are introduced together into the system leading to the fluorescence output signal as 1. Overall, the results indicate that the operation of the logic gate provides the recognition of ZA by the probe, HL.

The simultaneous presence of Zn^{2+} and OAc^- may be recognized through AND logic gate (Fig. 20). The output of an AND gate is only true when all the inputs are true. If one or more of an AND gate input are false, then the output is also false.

Fig. 20. AND logic gate diagram involving Zn^{2+} and OAc^- ions as inputs while fluorescence enhancement is attributed to the output.

HL interact with Zn^{2+} and OAc^- ions with prominent enhancement of the fluorescence intensity, so Zn^{2+} and OAc^- ions are two inputs and the fluorescence intensity change at 500 nm is the output.

For the input, the presence of Zn^{2+} and OAc^- are defined as 1, and their absence is defined as 0. For the output, the original emission intensity is considered as 0, and the enhanced fluorescence is defined as 1. The four possible input combinations are (0, 0), (1, 0), (0, 1) and (1, 1). With Zn^{2+} and OAc^- input alone, the output emission intensity changes are shown as 0.

To visualize the underlying electronic interaction and optimized geometry of HL and its ZA adduct, density functional theoretical (DFT) calculations have been performed using the 6-31G(d) basis set (Fig. 21). For [ZAL], only one OAc⁻ ion is bonded to Zn²⁺, also corroborated from its mass spectrum (Fig. 4). The highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) of HL and [ZAL] are shown in Fig. 12. The HOMO-LUMO energy gaps in HL and [ZAL] are 0.14252 eV and 0.122381 eV, respectively. Fig. 22 clearly indicates that the L-ZA adduct is stabilized by 0.02239 eV.

Fig. 21. Stereoscopic view of the energy optimized structures of HL (left) and [ZAL] systems (right).

Fig. 22. HOMO-LUMO energy gap of HL (left) and [ZAL] systems (right).

To have insight on the binding mode of HL with ZA, ¹H NMR titration is performed (Fig. 23). The naphthol OH undergoes a slight shift from 13.2492 ppm to 13.2692 ppm in presence of ZA. Upon further addition of ZA, this proton disappears. The imine proton (H²) is up-field shifted by 0.02 ppm from 9.9112 ppm to 9.8164 ppm, however no shift of the H³ proton signal (imine) indicates that the neighbouring N center of the imine group is prob-

Fig. 23. ¹H NMR spectral changes of HL upon gradual addition of ZA.

ably not involved for ZA coordination. The aromatic protons of naphthalene and benzene (H⁴ to H¹²) residues are up-field shifted. The phenol proton (H¹³) is hardly shifted, suggesting non-involvement of the oxygen donor towards ZA coordination. Thus, HL chelates ZA through imine nitrogen and deprotonated naphthol oxygen centers.

In summary, the new probe HL selectively detects ZA through significant fluorescence enhancement due to formation of a rigid structure involving imine nitrogen and naphthol oxygen while one OAc⁻ ion remains attached to Zn²⁺ (CHEF) along with inhibition of CH=N isomerization.

Human breast cancer cell imaging :

Human breast cancer cells (MCF7) treated only with HL (without ZA) are used as control. HL efficiently detects intracellular ZA. Fig. 24 indicates that HL permeates cells to stain ZA without any harm. Thus HL is useful to detect ZA in biological system.

Fig. 24. Fluorescence microscope image of MCF7 cells : (A) and (B) are photographs after incubating cells for 2 h with ZA (50 μM) and HL (20 μM) respectively while (C) is the photograph of cells after incubating with 50 μM ZA for 2 h followed by addition of 20 μM HL.

Conclusion

Single crystal X-ray structurally characterized probe HL selectively detects ZA both by colorimetric and fluo-

rescence method. The developed method allows construction of a molecular AND binary logic gate. The rapid turn on fluorescence is attributed to the CHEF assisted inhibition of CH=N isomerization, useful to monitor intracellular ZA in human breast cancer cell.

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Notes and references

CCDC number of HL is 1030760.

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